

Transforming Higher Education into Integrated Productive Institutions: A Conceptualization Review

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Abstract

This paper seeks a library search and evaluation of previous literature reviews on the subject of a methodological framework for transforming universities into integrated productive institutions. This paper has successfully developed a theoretical framework that is helpful for future research in this area. Besides, this study has provided new insight view on higher education institutions' studies and shifted the development of research from looking at the performance and success factors to a different angle which is identifying factors to improve the higher education institutions' survival. Nevertheless, as this is a conceptual paper, the main contribution is modeling innovative ideas to generate productive higher education institutions. On top of that, the model in this study is self-constructed with reference to the previous literature during and after Covid-19. Therefore, generalization is suitable to be applied. Further, the same study is encouraged to be implemented in different higher educational institutions and using different innovation drives. Therefore, by improving the use of innovation, higher education institutions' survival can be expanded to grow and flourish.

Keywords: *Transformation Universities, Community Partnership, Higher Education Challenges, Sustainability.*

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Introduction

There is no doubt that we live in a historical era in which we are faced with challenges that impose on us the inevitability of society transforming into a society in which the triad of science, technology and human development are interlinked (Al-Ansi, 2022). So, it acts as an effective engine to bring about sustainable quality progress capable of renewal and development. This can only be done by contributing to providing the development requirements of advanced knowledge, Original and innovative research projects, high-tech media, development of creative human powers, preparing leaders

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who own initiatives, forming positive trends towards science, literature and art within a sublime value system, providing the necessary resources, Keeping up with the knowledge and technology revolution. This is the essence of the function and philosophy of university education, which is the home of expertise, the bastion of thought in its various forms, and one of the main and effective components of the modern state (Garad et al., 2021).

Higher education institutions face a set of challenges, brought about by a set of local and global factors and forces that make its development a national demand, a life and societal imperative, to meet these challenges and the problems they pose, and the new and unprecedented opportunities and risks they bring (Bilen, 2010; Al-Ansi & Al-Ansi, 2023a). The future vision for the development of university education consists of envisioning a standard model that can serve as a frame of reference that can be guided in order to establish the constants and activate their performance, it also helps to identify strategic sites that have a multiplier effect on development and renewal, and thus the means by which the constants are effective, keep abreast of changes, and face challenges (Izak et al., 2017).

Moreover, any future conception of the development model depends on its time and location, subject to continuous review and recasting in the movement of the stampede between the forces of the institution within it and the factors, changes and challenges of society at the national and global levels (Aleixo et al., 2018). Based on the foregoing, this study aimed to suggest a methodological framework for transforming higher education institutions from a traditional educational institution into an integrated productive institution in light of the higher education institution's productive philosophy. It meets the needs of society, and keeps pace with global developments and changes. And that is by defining the philosophical framework of the producing higher education institution to activate community partnership, and benefit from some international experiences. To achieve these goals, the descriptive survey approach will be used, to identify the viewpoint of faculty members at the higher education institution on the importance of applying the proposed formula to activate the higher education institution's community partnership in light of the philosophy of the producing university and its obstacles, and to arrive at a suggested formula based on the following:

RO1. Determining the foundations and bases for the proposed formula and its objectives, the steps for building it, and the reasons and reasons for its construction

RO2. Exploring the requirements for activating the higher education institution's community partnership, and the proposed mechanisms for activating the higher education institution's community partnership.

RO3. Understanding the requirements for transforming higher education institutions into integrated productive institutions that meet the needs of society.

Methodology

The methodology used for this paper consists of a library search and evaluation of previous literature reviews on the subject of a methodological framework for transforming universities into integrated productive institutions. The library search encompasses online and offline materials to article journals and chapters in a book. References are based on online databases such as Web of Science, Scopus, Science Direct, and Google Scholar. The advanced search is limited to transforming

universities, and productive institutions. References are only taken from articles from journals, chapters from a book, and full-text documents. Thus, the limitations of this paper could be due to limited resources from databases as mentioned earlier as the search results also excluded Science and Health studies related to productive higher education institutions. Also, the higher education institutions' references are not restricted to one country but also take into consideration worldwide higher education institutions' progress from 2000 until 2023.

Results

Based on the conceptual review of previous studies, we review the following the most important points extracted related to the transformation of higher education institutions into productive institutions, challenges and opportunities, increasing income and requirements for building mutually beneficial relationships with society and activating the community partnership of the university in light of the philosophy of the productive university, which are as follows:

Higher Education Institutions: Challenges and Opportunities

The persistent issues that higher education institutions, particularly in developing nations, encounter. The following are some of the most pressing issues and challenges (Bilen, 2010; Aleixo et al., 2018; Goddard & Puukka, 2008):

- Failure to specify the type of education that the educational system aspires to provide. Is it for research or knowledge education?
- Lack of interest in practical research, a lack of funds to assist scientific research, and a lack of openness to support scientific research from local and foreign higher education institutions.
- Prioritizing quantity over quality in specialization repetition and lack of competitiveness, as well as the accumulation of students in particular specializations without others, without taking into account market demand for specializations without others.
- The lack of a culture of evaluation and correction inside university institutions, which includes methods for collecting reliable data that allows those in authority to make decisions that improve educational efficiency.
- Higher education has failed to respond to the economy's needs and job prospects.
- Academic standards have deteriorated, there has been a massive increase in the number of students, and there is a lack of equipment.
- There are few options to communicate with the outside world and cooperate with international educational institutions.
- The inability of universities to adopt advanced patterns and technologies due to a lack of advanced technology capabilities in the sectors of information and communication.
- The slowness with which colleges and higher education institutions respond to the demands of change.
- Failure to keep up with technological and knowledge advancements, as well as a reduction in development and innovation activities.

The COVID-19 pandemic has had a significant impact on higher education, both in the short-term and the long-term. In the short-term, the pandemic has forced many universities to move to online learning, which has presented a number of challenges, including (Rashid & Yadav, 2020; Toquero, 2020; Pokhrel & Chhetri, 2021):

- **Technology access and support:** Not all students have equal access to technology, and some students may need additional support to learn effectively online.
- **Student engagement:** Online learning can be more isolating than in-person learning, and it can be more difficult for students to stay engaged.
- **Assessment:** It can be more difficult to assess student learning in an online environment.
- In the long-term, the pandemic has also raised a number of challenges for higher education, including (Simamora et al., 2020; Turnbull et al., 2021; Al-Ansi & Al-Ansi, 2023b):
 - **Financial sustainability:** The pandemic has led to a decline in enrolment and revenue for many universities, which has put a strain on their financial sustainability.
 - **The future of work:** The pandemic has accelerated the pace of change in the workforce, and universities need to prepare students for the jobs of the future.
 - **The digital divide:** The pandemic has highlighted the digital divide, and universities need to find ways to ensure that all students have access to the technology and resources they need to succeed.

Despite these challenges, there are also a number of opportunities for higher education in the post-COVID-19 world. For example, the pandemic has accelerated the adoption of online learning, which can make higher education more accessible to students around the world (Al-Ansi et al., 2023). Additionally, the pandemic has highlighted the importance of lifelong learning, and higher education institutions can play a key role in helping students upskill and reskill for the jobs of the future.

Overall, the COVID-19 pandemic has presented a number of challenges for higher education. However, there are also a number of opportunities for universities to adapt and thrive in the post-COVID-19 world. By addressing the challenges head-on and seizing the opportunities, universities can play a vital role in preparing students for the future.

The Foundations for Productive Universities

The foundations and bases for productive higher education institutions are as follows (Middaugh 2001; Okoro & Agugum, 2017; Bonfield et al., 2020; Gupta & Yadav, 2021):

- **A strong faculty.** A productive higher education institution has a strong faculty of scholars and researchers who are engaged in cutting-edge research and teaching.
- **A supportive environment.** A productive higher education institution provides a supportive environment for faculty and students to do their best work. This includes providing adequate resources, such as funding, facilities, and technology.
- **A clear mission.** A productive higher education institution has a clear mission that is shared by all members of the community. This mission provides a sense of purpose and direction for the university.

- **A commitment to excellence.** A productive higher education institution is committed to excellence in all aspects of its work, from teaching and research to student life.
- **A focus on innovation.** A productive higher education institution is constantly innovating and looking for new ways to improve its programs and services.
- **A strong alumni network.** A productive higher education institution has a strong alumni network that is engaged with the university and its mission. This network can provide support for students, faculty, and the university as a whole.

By building on these foundations, universities can create a productive environment that fosters innovation and excellence.

Here are some additional factors that can contribute to a productive higher education institution (Dundar & Lewis, 1998; Aithal & Kumar, 2015; Connell, 2019; Gontareva et al., 2019, Magolda, 2020):

- **A diverse student body.** A diverse student body brings a variety of perspectives and experiences to the higher education institutions, which can lead to new ideas and insights.
- **A commitment to diversity and inclusion.** Productive higher education institutions are committed to diversity and inclusion, which creates a welcoming and supportive environment for all students.
- **A focus on student success.** A productive higher education institution is focused on student success, and provides students with the resources and support they need to succeed.
- **A strong community.** A productive higher education institution has a strong sense of community, which can help students feel connected and supported.

By focusing on these factors, universities can create a productive environment that is conducive to learning and growth.

Steps for Transforming Higher Education Institutions into Productive Institutions

Here is a proposed methodological framework for transforming universities from a traditional educational institution into an integrated productive higher education institution in light of the university's productive philosophy (Findler et al., 2019; Balzer, 2020; Gupta & Yadav, 2020):

Step 1: Identify the higher education institution's productive philosophy. What is the higher education institution's mission? What are its goals? What are its values?

Step 2: Assess the higher education institution's current state. What are the university's strengths? What are its weaknesses? What are its opportunities? What are its threats?

Step 3: Develop a plan for transformation. This plan should outline the steps that the higher education institutions will take to become an integrated productive higher education institution. The plan should be specific, measurable, achievable, relevant, and time-bound.

Step 4: Implement the plan. This will require the commitment and effort of all members of the higher education institutions community.

Step 5: Evaluate the plan. This will help to ensure that the higher education institutions are on track to achieve its goals.

Step 6: Make adjustments as needed. The plan may need to be adjusted as the higher education institutions progresses.

Step 7: Celebrate success. The higher education institutions should celebrate its successes along the way. This will help to keep everyone motivated.

Here are some additional considerations for transforming universities into integrated productive higher education institutions (Kopp et al., 2019; Benavides et al., 2020):

- **The role of technology.** Technology can play a major role in transforming universities into integrated productive institutions. Technology can be used to improve teaching and learning, to facilitate research, and to connect with the community.

- **The role of partnerships.** Universities can partner with businesses, government agencies, and other organizations to create a more productive environment. Partnerships can provide universities with access to resources, expertise, and opportunities.

- **The role of funding.** Funding is essential for transforming universities into integrated productive higher education institutions. Universities need funding to support research, to develop new programs, and to hire new faculty.

By following these steps, universities can transform themselves into integrated productive higher education institutions that are better equipped to meet the needs of the 21st century.

Higher Education Institutions and Community Partnership

The requirements for activating a higher education institution's community partnership vary depending on the specific partnership and the university's policies. However, some common requirements include (Leal Filho et al., 2019; Holland, 2019; Saleh & Mujahiddin, 2020; Cockell et al., 2020):

- **Identifying a community partner.** The first step is to identify a community partner that is interested in working with the higher education institutions. This could be a local non-profit organization, government agency, or business.

- **Developing a partnership agreement.** Once a community partner has been identified, the next step is to develop a partnership agreement. This document should outline the goals of the partnership, the roles and responsibilities of each partner, and the timeline for the partnership.

- **Obtaining funding.** In some cases, funding may be required to support the partnership. The higher education institutions may be able to provide funding, or the community partner may be able to secure funding from other sources.

- **Providing training and support.** It is important to provide training and support to the individuals who will be involved in the partnership. This will help to ensure that the partnership is successful.

- **Evaluating the partnership.** It is important to evaluate the partnership on a regular basis to ensure that it is meeting its goals. This will help to identify any areas where the partnership can be improved.

In addition to these requirements, there may be other specific requirements that are unique to the higher education institutions or the community partner. It is important

to check with the higher education institutions and the community partner to determine the specific requirements for activating the partnership.

Here are some additional tips for activating a higher education institution's community partnership (Purcell et al., 2019; Sonetti et al., 2019; Chankseliani et al., 2021):

- **Be clear about the goals of the partnership.** What do you hope to achieve by working with the community partner?
- **Be flexible and willing to compromise.** Partnerships are not always easy, and there will be times when you need to be willing to compromise.
- **Communicate effectively.** Communication is key to the success of any partnership. Make sure to communicate regularly with the community partner about the partnership's progress.
- **Celebrate successes.** When the partnership achieves a goal, take the time to celebrate the success. This will help to keep everyone motivated and engaged.

By following these tips, you can increase your chances of activating a successful higher education institution's community partnership.

Higher Education Institutions and Increasing Income

There are a number of methods that higher education institutions can use to increase their income. Some of these methods include (Cantwell, 2019; Al-Ansi & Fatmawati, 2023; Mitchell et al., 2019; Blankenberger & Williams, 2020; Ehrenberg, 2020):

- **Tuition increases:** Tuition is the most common source of revenue for higher education institutions. However, tuition increases can be unpopular with students and parents.
- **Government funding:** Government funding is another important source of revenue for higher education institutions. However, government funding is often limited, and it can be difficult to secure.
- **Corporate partnerships:** Corporate partnerships can provide higher education institutions with funding, as well as access to resources and expertise.
- **Charitable donations:** Charitable donations from alumni, parents, and other supporters can provide a significant source of revenue for higher education institutions.
- **Venture capital:** Venture capital can be used to fund new initiatives and programs at higher education institutions. However, venture capital can be risky, and it is not always available.
- **Selling assets:** Higher education institutions can sell assets, such as real estate, to generate revenue. However, selling assets can be a controversial decision, and it is not always possible to generate significant revenue.
- **Online learning:** Online learning can be a way to reach more students and generate additional revenue. However, online learning can be expensive to develop and deliver.

The best method for increasing income will vary depending on the specific circumstances of the higher education institution. However, by considering all of the options available, institutions can find ways to increase their revenue and ensure their long-term financial sustainability.

In addition to the methods listed above, higher education institutions can also increase their income by (Higher Education Commission, 2014; Sazonov et al., 2015; Lucianelli & Citro, 2017; Modugno & Di Carlo, 2019; Almagtome et al., 2019):

- **Improving efficiency:** By reducing costs and streamlining operations, higher education institutions can free up resources that can be used to increase income.
- **Expanding programs:** By offering new programs and courses, higher education institutions can attract more students and generate additional revenue.
- **Marketing and branding:** By effectively marketing and branding themselves, higher education institutions can increase their visibility and attract more students.

By taking these steps, higher education institutions can increase their income and ensure their long-term financial sustainability.

In addition, cooperation between higher education and other organizations can take many forms, including (Tynjälä et al., 2003; Deem et al., 2008; De Wit et al., 2015):

- **Joint research projects:** Organizations can provide funding for research projects that are of interest to both the institution and the organization. This can help to advance knowledge in areas such as financial markets, economic development, and social policy.
- **Student internships:** Organizations can offer internships to students at higher education institutions. This can provide students with valuable work experience and help them to develop their skills and knowledge.
- **Career development programs:** Organizations can partner with higher education institutions to offer career development programs for students and alumni. These programs can provide students with information about the financial industry, help them to develop their job search skills, and connect them with potential employers.
- **Financial literacy education:** Organizations can partner with higher education institutions to offer financial literacy education to students and the general public. This can help to improve financial literacy and financial decision-making.
- **Donations:** Organizations can make donations to higher education institutions to support scholarships, academic programs, and other initiatives.

Examples of Specific Partnerships between Higher Education Institutions and other Organizations

Cooperation between higher education institutions and other organizations can benefit both parties. Organizations can gain access to new knowledge and talent, while higher education institutions can gain access to financial resources and support for their programs and initiatives.

Here are some examples of specific partnerships between higher education institutions and other organizations (Johnstone-Louis, 2017; Al-Ansi, 2022; São Paulo, 2019):

- **The University of Chicago Booth School of Business and Goldman Sachs:** The University of Chicago Booth School of Business and Goldman Sachs have partnered to create the Goldman Sachs 10,000 Women program, which provides financial education and training to women entrepreneurs in developing countries.
- **The Massachusetts Institute of Technology and Credit Suisse:** The Massachusetts Institute of Technology and Credit Suisse have partnered to create the

MIT Sloan Credit Suisse Innovation Lab, which brings together MIT students, faculty, and researchers with Credit Suisse employees to work on innovative solutions to financial challenges.

- **The University of Pennsylvania and JPMorgan Chase:** The University of Pennsylvania and JPMorgan Chase have partnered to create the JPMorgan Chase Center for Financial Services Innovation, which conducts research on financial innovation and provides training to financial professionals.

These are just a few examples of the many ways that higher education institutions and other institutions can cooperate. As the world becomes increasingly interconnected, these partnerships will become even more important in helping to address the challenges and opportunities of the 21st century.

Figure 1. A Proposed Methodological Framework for Increasing Income for Higher Education Institutions

Points of Transformation Higher Education Institutions

Here is a methodological framework for transforming higher education institutions from a traditional educational institution into an integrated productive institution in light of the higher education institution's productive philosophy:

- **Identify the university's strengths and weaknesses.** The first step is to identify the university's strengths and weaknesses in terms of its ability to be productive. This can be done through a SWOT analysis, which will identify the university's strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats.
- **Develop a vision for the future.** Once the university's strengths and weaknesses have been identified, it is important to develop a vision for the future of

the university. This vision should be based on the university's strengths and weaknesses, as well as the needs of the community.

- **Create a plan to achieve the vision.** Once the vision has been developed, it is important to create a plan to achieve it. This plan should include specific goals, objectives, and strategies.

- **Implement the plan.** Once the plan has been created, it is important to implement it. This will require the commitment of all members of the university community.

- **Evaluate the plan.** It is important to evaluate the plan on a regular basis to ensure that it is meeting its goals. This will help to identify any areas that need improvement.

By following this framework, higher education institutions can transform themselves into integrated productive institutions that are better able to meet the needs of their students and the world.

Here are some specific strategies that higher education institutions can use to become more productive:

- **Focus on student outcomes.** Higher education institutions should focus on helping students achieve their academic and career goals. This means providing students with the resources and support they need to succeed.

- **Foster innovation.** Higher education institutions should encourage innovation and creativity among their faculty and students. This can be done by providing funding for research and development, and by creating an environment that is supportive of new ideas.

- **Partner with the community.** Higher education institutions should partner with the community to address local challenges. This can be done by providing educational and training programs, or by conducting research on local issues.

- **Become a global leader.** Higher education institutions should strive to be global leaders in education, research, and innovation. This can be done by attracting top students and faculty from around the world, and by conducting research that has a global impact.

By implementing these strategies, higher education institutions can become more productive institutions that are better able to meet the needs of their students, the world, and the future.

Formula to Activate the Higher Education Institution's Community Partnership

Here is a proposed formula to activate the higher education institution's community partnership in light of the philosophy of the producing university and its obstacles:

Formula:

- o **Identify the community's needs.** The first step is to identify the needs of the community that the university is located in. This can be done through surveys, interviews, and focus groups.

- o **Match university resources with community needs.** Once the community's needs have been identified, the higher education institution can then match its

resources with those needs. This could involve providing access to research, expertise, or facilities.

- **Create a partnership agreement.** Once the higher education institution and the community have agreed on the terms of the partnership, they should create a written agreement. This will help to ensure that both parties are on the same page and that the partnership is successful.
- **Provide ongoing support.** Partnerships are not always easy, and they require ongoing support from both parties. The higher education institutions should provide the community with resources and support to help them achieve their goals.

Obstacles:

There are a number of obstacles that can prevent higher education institutions from forming successful community partnerships. These include:

- **Lack of trust.** Communities may be hesitant to partner with higher education institutions if they feel that the university is not interested in their needs.
- **Lack of resources.** Higher education institutions may not have the resources to support community partnerships.
- **Lack of communication.** Higher education institutions and communities may not communicate effectively, which can lead to misunderstandings and conflict.

Recommendations

To overcome these obstacles, higher education institutions should:

- **Build trust with the community.** This can be done by listening to the community's needs and concerns, and by being transparent about the higher education institution's goals.
- **Invest in community partnerships.** Higher education institutions should allocate resources to support community partnerships. This could include funding, staff, and time.
- **Communicate effectively with the community.** This means being clear about the goals of the partnership, and listening to the community's feedback.

By following these steps, universities can form successful community partnerships that benefit both the higher education institutions and the community.

Conclusion

This paper has successfully developed a theoretical framework that is helpful for future research in this area. Besides, this study has provided a new insight view on higher education institutions' studies and shifted the development of business research from looking at the performance and success factors to a different angle which is identifying factors to improve the higher education institutions' survival. The understanding of higher education institutions' survival significance may lead to the effort in promoting innovation in business. Theoretically, social networking, computerized record and online marketing are the main variables that were found to be significant to higher education institutions survival but empirical data is required to prove these connections. Nevertheless, as this is a conceptual paper, there is no data collected to

enable generalization to other countries. On top of that, the framework in this study is self-constructed with reference to the previous literature. Therefore, generalization is not suitable to be applied. Further, the same study is encouraged to be done in other countries and using different innovation drives. Therefore, by improving the use of innovation, higher education institutions' survival can be expanded to grow and flourish.

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